

Research Capacity among Faculty and Staff of DMMC Institute of Health Sciences

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Abstract:- A sustainable research culture is important in achieving the institution's mission and vision. Research is one of the driving forces that assists and supports educational managers in their decision-making. The Leaders of the school such as the President, Vice-president for academic affairs, Deans, and Research Director must act and determine the status of the research culture of DMMCIHS in terms of the research readiness of the personnel and the status of research promotion. The purpose of the study is to discover the status of the DMMCIHS research capacity. For this study, a questionnaire was constructed, validated, and tested showing a high-reliability coefficient in the construct measured. A total sampling was used with the intention of examining the entire population of the institution. The instrument was administered during the strategic planning and annual operations planning for the academic year 2021-2022, findings result that there is a high level of readiness to conduct educational research, however, the research promotion practices, and status of research culture as rated by the respondents were good levels. The implication of the study is the further enhancement of research promotion practices to produce very knowledgeable, motivated, and skilful researchers.

Keywords:- Research Culture, Research Promotion Practices, Research Readiness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tertiary education is certainly a big investment and the knowledge generated by research will be the basis of sustainable development. One of the most distinguished and competitive strengths of tertiary schools is research. The importance of research culture in higher education is very substantial but is often neglected. Studies identified that [2] to be able to sustain research in an organization, "it must be part of the organization's way of institutional actions – its culture". Administrators of tertiary educational institutions must have a holistic understanding of how research becomes embedded in their institutional practice because it can suggest collaborative and reflective interventions for improvement, including leadership and organizational development. This situation demands that tertiary educational institutions must develop a culture centred on research and innovation. In relation to these, the interest in educational research in other tertiary education has vastly increased in recent years. This means that DMMCIHS faculty and staff must be equipped

with the necessary and advanced skills and capability to conduct research and produce outputs.

Furthermore, research is a fundamental mission and major function of tertiary education in view of the scarcity of research in Philippine higher education institutions (HEIs), it is the reason why the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) mandated the improvement of research productivity [4]. However, there are seven major factors [1] that lead to low research productivity in selected Philippine HEIs, this includes limited time, lack of training on publication, fear of rejection, lack of interest, faculty laziness, and lack of institutional support.

Research culture depends on several factors [3] which include institutional research policies and agenda; developmental culture and working conditions; budget allocations for research; infrastructure; collaboration with and access to research professionals in other institutions; policies and guidelines about research benefits and incentives; research committees; and publications.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The researcher in this study is interested in evaluating the 1. readiness of the respondent in terms of cognitive, psychomotor, and affective skills, 2. determining the level of research promotion practices of DMMCIHS in terms of policies, technical assistance, or support such as de-loading, provision of software and the like, professional regulations or support in memberships in the research association, faculty involvement like peer coaching and lastly 3. to determine the status of research culture in terms of capability, productivity, dissemination, and utilization in research.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The author used the descriptive-correlational method, and total sampling was used with the intention of examining the entire population (45 respondents) of the institution. The researcher utilized a self-made questionnaire which was formulated based on the information that was gathered using books and the internet. The survey questionnaire was composed of two parts. Part 1 dealt with the respondents' level of research readiness, part 2 covered the level of research promotion and part determined the status of the research culture of DMMCIHS.

The administration of the instrument took place during the strategic planning and annual operations planning for the academic year 2021-2022. Prior to this, the researchers briefed the respondents about the contents and purposes of the study. A consent form was also given to the respondents to ensure their confidentiality and anonymity. The researcher

assured them of their anonymity and the confidentiality of the information they provided. After the retrieval of the questionnaires, it was tallied and subjected to statistical treatment with the guidance of the researcher’s statistician.

A. Validation of Instrument

Since the questionnaire was not standardized it was presented first to quantitative research experts in educational management, and statistics for validation. Their comments and suggestion were incorporated into the final draft and tested showing a high-reliability coefficient The following results were obtained using Cronbach’s Alpha: knowledge (0.852), attitude (0.778), skills (0.90), research promotion practices (0.893) and status of research culture (0.782) before its distribution to the respondents.

B. Statistical Treatment of Data

The researcher utilized the following statistical tool:

- Weighted Mean, used to determine the (a) respondents’ level of research readiness along knowledge, attitude, and skills, (b) level of research promotion practices of HEIs, and (c) status of the research culture of DMMCIHS as rated by the respondents.

- Pearson r, used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the (a) respondents’ level of research readiness and level of research promotion practices, (b) respondents’ level of research readiness and status of the research culture, and (c) level of research promotion practices and status of research culture

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the summary of the level of research readiness having an overall high interpretation and a weighted mean of 3.43. The Attitude indicator had the highest weighted mean of 3.68, having a Very high interpretation. The table clearly identifies the positive attitude of the respondents towards research.

Table 1: Level of Research Readiness

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Knowledge	3.28	High	3
Attitude	3.68	Very High	1
Skills	3.33	High	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.43	High	

The literature review agrees that research culture is influenced by two sets of faculties [4]. First is the “pro research” faculty who contribute to productivity. Second, are those who are ambivalent towards the research activities yet

may be willing to be involved if properly oriented and supported, these findings imply that the faculty has a positive perspective towards research if support is given to enhance their knowledge and skills

Table 2: Level of Research Promotion Practices

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Institutional Policy	2.80	High	4
Technical Assistance	3.12	High	2
Professional Regulations	3.20	High	1
Faculty Involvement	2.88	High	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.00	High	

In Table 2. all have the same High interpretations, but the indicator for the professional regulations tops the rank with a weighted mean of 3.20, and the institutional policy at the least has a weighted mean of 2.80, this implies that some respondents have a low remark. The result implies that

although the interpretation is all Agree, the institutional policy and faculty involvement are not strong compared to professional regulations and technical assistance, it may be suggestive that there is a need to enhance the institutional policy and faculty involvement.

Table 3: Status of Research Culture

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Research Capability	2.74	Good	2
Research Productivity	2.80	Good	1
Research Dissemination	2.44	Developing	3
Research Utilization	2.42	Developing	4
Overall Weighted Mean	2.60	Good	

Table 3 displays split interpretations the first having a weighted mean of 2.80 is Research Productivity and followed by Research Capability with a weighted mean of 2.74. The other two indicators are Research Dissemination having a

weighted mean of 2.44 and the least Research Utilization which has a weighted mean of 2.42. The data implies that the indicators with Good verbal interpretation had responses of Agree which means DMMCIHS supports the research

capability and productivity meanwhile having difficulty in research dissemination and utilization. Nevertheless, the overall weight is 2.60 with a Good interpretation.

A research culture can be described in two ways: (1) A developing research culture that still needs a strong mentoring system and proactive research training and capability while (2) an established research culture is marked with excellent quality research that is published and cited internationally.

Table 4: Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Readiness and Level of Research on Institutional Policy

Level of Readiness	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge	0.357	0.000	Significant
Attitude	0.117	0.244	Not Significant
Skills	0.299	0.003	Significant

A significant relationship was noted between respondents' knowledge ($r = 0.357, p = 0.000$) and skills ($r = 0.299, p = 0.003$) and promotion practices along institutional policy of table 4, both p values are lower than 0.01 test of

significance. This implies that when the respondents show a high level of knowledge and skills, the higher the level of promotion practices along the institutional policy.

Table 5: Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Readiness and Level of Research Promotion Practices on Technical Assistance

Level of Readiness	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge	0.320	0.001	Significant
Attitude	0.314	0.001	Significant
Skills	0.337	0.001	Significant

0.01 level of significance

Table 5 displays a significant relationship between respondents' knowledge ($r = 0.320, p = 0.001$), attitude ($r = 0.314, p = 0.001$) and skills ($r = 0.337, p = 0.001$) and promotion practices along Technical assistance, both p values

are less than 0.01 test of significance. This implies that when the participants show a high level of knowledge, the higher the level of research promotion practices along with technical assistance.

Table 6: Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Readiness and Level of Research Promotion Practices on Professional Regulations

Level of Readiness	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge	-0.171	0.088	Not Significant
Attitude	0.347	0.000*	Significant
Skills	0.222	0.026**	Significant

*0.01 level of significance

**0.05 level of significance

No Significant relationship was noted in Table 6 between the readiness of the respondents along knowledge and research promotion practices along professional regulations as shown by the Pearson r, the value of -0.171 and a p-value of 0.88 which is higher than the test of significance at 0.05.

test of significance. This implies that when members of the academic community of radiologic technology show a high level of readiness along attitude and skills, the higher is the level of the promotion practices along professional regulations.

However, a significant relationship was noted between respondents' attitudes ($r = 0.347, p = 0.000$) and skills ($r = -0.222, p = 0.026$) with both p values that are lower than the

This implies that the higher the level of readiness in terms of attitude and skills towards research practices of the faculty the more support is given by the institution to push the faculty to be more productive.

Table 7: Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Readiness and Level of Research Promotion Practices on Faculty Involvement

Level of Readiness	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge	-0.088	0.383	Not Significant
Attitude	0.310	0.002	Significant
Skills	-0.088	0.385	Not Significant

Table 7 displays no significant relationship between respondents' level of readiness along with knowledge and skills between research promotion practices along faculty involvement.

However, a significant relationship was noted between respondents' attitudes which are lower than the test of significance at 0.01. The result from this table implies that when the faculty and staff show a high level of readiness

along attitude, the higher the level of promotion practices along the participant's involvement was provided.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The respondents' level of research readiness is high.
- The level of research promotion practices is High.
- The status of the research culture of DMMCIHS is at the level of good status but very close to developing status.
- The higher the level of the research promotion practice, the higher the respondents' level of readiness.

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following are offered as recommendations for possible actions:

- The level of the participants' research readiness must be supported by a high level of research productivity, dissemination, and utilization of research findings.
- Premised on these findings, it is therefore strongly recommended that DMMCIHS should further strengthen the research promotion practices enhancing the research culture by building scholarly skills and capacity, boosting the morale and motivation of the participants, and strengthening their engagement in research-related activities.
- The results of this study are surely not a solution or remedy to the current situation of research culture DMMCIHS, but it is hoped that they point a direction to tap strengths, identify weaknesses, explore opportunities, and eliminate the threats to the development of research culture.
- Future research can be done to have an in-depth investigation including the research promotion practices and level of research culture in terms of research productivity, research dissemination, and research production.

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